

Acid Wash Duration and its Impact on Denim Garment Properties: An Investigation into Optimal Washing Times

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17660443](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17660443)

KEYWORDS

Washing
Denim Washing
Acid Wash
Color Fastness
Mechanical
Performance

ABSTRACT

This study deals with the effect of acid wash treatment on denim garments by using three different washing time intervals 5, 10 and 15 minutes. By varying the washing time under fixed conditions, the study is undertaken for proposing an effective exposure time which will lead to optimum level of fading having least damage in fabrics. Acid washing throughout the denim industry is a popular finishing process used to give the fabric surface a certain vintage and faded effect. But the time taken for acid treatment is an important factor in both aesthetic appearance, and physical characteristics of the fabric. Performance tests such as rubbing fastness, pH value, tear strength, color fastness, shrinking and hand feel were carried out to investigate the variation of low quality factors with different acid wash durations in the present study. The results illuminate the relationship between the duration of acid exposure (longer or shorter) on both durability and comfort, as well as aesthetics in denim. Results show that washing with an acid during 10 min is the best compromise between visual and performance needs, as it allows to keep acceptable mechanical properties for the fabrics and colour fastness properties, pH of the system while providing a faded appearance more visually satisfying.

1. INTRODUCTION

As an extensively utilised material in the world fashion sector, the denim has become popular for its strength, comfort and classical appeal with respect to wears like jeans, jackets etc [1]. Its multifunctional characteristics have given rise to several finishing treatments (enzyme, stone and acid washing) which are used in order to improve the aesthetic of the fabric[2]. Among these methods acid washing is the most well-

known, for its ability to create contrasting 'washed out', vintage effects by removing a portion of the indigo colour from its base fibre[3]. This process does not only change the visual appearance it also modifies many of the important physical and chemical properties of denim including fabric strength, shrinkage, pH level and comfort[4].

In recent years, the acid washed process has attracted much attention due to possibility of

achieving creatively new faded and old looking appearances[5]. But, in this context, despite such popularity, the influence of washing time on properties have not been enough studied. The effects of acid washing on denim have been well researched and in particular, the acid wash using different methods such as phosphoric acid and potassium permanganate treatment and its impact on fabric properties[6]. For instance, Haq et al. and Hossain et al. demonstrate that acid washing has been shown to enhance aesthetic performance, such as color fading while also diminishing tensile strength, fabric weight, and colour depth[7, 8]. Other studies also indicated the conflict between visual effects and fabric durability [9, 10]. Though valuable information can be obtained by these studies on the effects of acid washing; they do not systematically investigate the effect of different durations of acid washes upon certain quality aspects of denim, including rub fastness, colorfastness and shrinkage[6, 11]. In addition, there is a lack of comprehension on the effects that various times of washing (5, 10 and 15 min) have in global performance of the fabric.

This research aims to fill this gap by looking at the effect of various levels of acid wash time on the physical and chemical properties of denim garments. This study investigates, as a function of different acid washing times (i.e., 5 minutes, 10 minutes and 15minutes), what is the best time for washing so that it may give a dyeing effect on fabric's visual appeal, but also be optimal in respect to strength of fabric. Specifically, the research discusses the effect of the Wash time on important factors such as Rubbing fastness, Tear strength, pH value, Moisture content, Color fastness and Shrinkage. The understanding of such effects is important in order not only to attain an appealing look of acid-washed denim, but also to maintain its durability, comfort and performance. The study will deliver, in due time, practical recommendations for the optimization of the "acid wash" process proper of denim production, always looking for the best harmony and compatible trade-off between appealing garments and harsh requirement from daily performances.

2. MATERIALS & METHOD

2.1 Raw Materials and Chemicals

A denim pant (100% cotton, 3/1 right-hand twill) was utilized for performing the study. Potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$) was one oxidizing agent. It is water-soluble, having a pH

of about 7.0-7.5 for a 1% solution. Another inorganic acid was Phosphoric Acid (PAP) also soluble in water and the pH value of 1% aqueous solution being about from 1.5 to 2.0. Both of the chemicals were kept in a cool place. Lightweight, hard stones with a diameter of approximately 2–4 cm, acid wash balls called Muri Balls were utilized. They are gray to pale beige in color and are pH neutral. The details and properties of these chemicals are obtained from the reliable chemical suppliers, hatkhola, Bangladesh.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Each sample was cut and measured to ensure uniformity in weight, size, and fabric construction. The garments were divided into three groups to be treated for 5, 10, & 15 minutes respectively.

2.3 Preparation of Acid Wash Solution

The method included the preparation of a solution of Potassium Permanganate by dissolving an exact volume of potassium permanganate in water. A neutralization solution of PAP was also made at 5 g/L, for post-wash neutralization. Enough water was used to entirely submerge the clothes for washing, and mud balls were added to help with abrasion, helping in cleaning and washing.

2.4 Acid Washing Procedure

The denim trousers and Muri Balls were put into the laundry machine. Then, add the prepared Potassium Permanganate solution to the machine. Both species of samples are washed at the room temperature for different time periods; the 1st sample was washed for 5 min, the 2nd sample was washed for a period of 10 min and, and finally, the third sample was washed for a duration of tactically equal to 15 minutes. The $KMnO_4$ solution was emptied after each washing cycle and articles are washed with plenty of pure water. The PAP solution was then neutralized by rinsing the garments with Acid PAP cleaner for 10 minutes to eliminate chemical residues and to adjust the pH of the fabric. The clothes were then washed once more in clear water to rinse away the neutralizing agents completely.

2.5 Drying and Conditioning Procedure

The denim garment was then dried at a room temperature or in the case of low temperatures (tumble-dried) by using a drier. They were then conditioned for 24 h at $(21 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ and $(65 \pm 2)\%$ relative humidity without any testing.

2.6 Characterization

2.6.1 Tear Strength Test

The Tear Strength test of acid-washed denim clothes determines the strength of fabric against tearing after subjected to chemical treatments such as Potassium Permanganate washing and neutralization. It was tested according to ASTM D1424 and a Tear Strength Tester, Digital Elmendorf Tear Tester (James Heals, ELMATEAR 1555, UK). The test consisted in cutting fabric samples along warp and fill directions in 100 X 75 mm in size, clamping the samples and pulling them with the testing machine. Tearing force in Newton (N) was used to evaluate the tear resistance of the fabric.

2.6.2 Shrinkage Test

Acid Washed Denim Garments Shrinkage test is used to determine the dimensional stability of the fabric after washing. The test assesses the percentage (%) difference in a fabric size, while the garments retain their original fit and shape as a result of water and chemical treatments. Shrinkage% was measured by this formula

$$\text{Shrinkage \%} = ((\text{Original length} - \text{Final length}) / \text{Original length}) \times 100$$

2.6.3 Color Fastness to Washing

The Color Fastness to washing test of acid-washed garments is a measure of the fabric's resistance to change in color when simultaneously subjected to washing. This test was performed by following the ISO 105-C06 method after washing the samples in Launderometer. The comparison of color change was done using a Gray Scale for Color Change.

2.6.4 Color Fastness to Rubbing

Rubbing fastness determines how well the acid-wash denim maintains its color when exposed to dry or wet friction, which is a huge part of what the fabric is actually used for. This test is performed using Crockmeter, the samples were rub 10 times with a dry cotton rubbing

cloth, then with a wet one. The transferred color on the cloth was evaluated using a Gray Scale.

2.6.5 pH Test

The pH test allows to determinate if wet processing has been thoroughly neutralized after washing, bleaching, dyeing or another wet process. pH test was done using the Digital pH Meter, following ISO 3071:2005. 2 gram of fabric sample soaked for 2 hours and checked the pH label.

2.6.6 GSM Measurement

GSM testing reveals the weight of fabric per unit area and indicates uniformity of weave construction and performance post wash. It allows checking the denim for requirements specification of weight, strength and handle and also checks on bulk production. In this study, GSM was measured using GSM Cutter machine and calculated in oz/yd^2 .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tear Strength Test Analysis

Fig. 1: Tear strength test

Tear strength test results indicate that the acid washing has a significant impact on the denim, where warp is stronger than weft. The tear strength of the warp is 20.63 N and of the weft 18.56 N before washing, which both decrease after washing, with a bigger decrease in weft direction. Tear strength of warp and weft, respectively, 20.58 N and 14.73 N are achieved after washing for 15 min (weft is more likely to be weakened by acid washing than warp owned to the fibre constitution).

3.2 Shrinkage test result analysis

3.3 Color Fastness to Wash test Result Analysis

Fig. 2: Color fastness to wash test

For acid-washed denim fabric, the colour staining test data indicate very low degree of stains for multifiber samples after different washing period (5, 10 and 15 min). The color staining scale values of the fabric samples such as cotton, nylon, polyester, acrylic and wool are generally similar to each other (4-5). The findings indicate that there are no significant influences of acid washing on the colour staining characteristics of the fabric since its staining values (regardless of time intervals applied) did not substantially change. However, some differences among fibers are observed in the amount of staining with wool and nylon being slightly more stained than acetate or polyester. These findings suggest that the acid wash treatment affects tear strength more, size of change in color and degree of staining with less.

3.4 Color Fastness to rubbing test analysis

Fig. 3: Color fastness to rubbing test

Color fastness test results of the acid-washed denim fabric are representative of how washing effect has impacted dry and wet crocking resistance. Prior to washing, the dry and wet crocking results are low, where a grade is 1 of the former and slightly higher at grade 2 of the latter. 3 The dry crocking resistance increases to 4 after washing for a duration of 5 minutes and the wet crocking resistance is also brought up to 4. When washed again after 10 and 15 min, and dried or wet, the grade in dry or wet crocking rises to nearly 4. These results indicate that acid washing improves the colour fastness of fabrics, more so in wet crocking. The denim is initially rated low, but its ability to resist color transfer from dry rubbing increases over the number of washings. Nevertheless, dry crocking is still in the red region less than 5 and wet crocking ratings are even lower compared to the maximal rating of 5. This means that though acid washing does improve color fastness, fabric colored by it faces an extent of rubbing induced color loss.

3.5 pH Test Result Analysis

Table 1: pH observation of the samples

Samples	pH
Wash for 5 min	7.8
Wash for 10 min	5.6
Wash for 15 min	5.9

The pH test results of the acid-washed denim fabric in Fig. 1 indicate that the pH value decreases with increasing washing time. At the beginning, 5 minutes after washing, pH is 7.8 suggesting a neutral or slightly alkaline environment. After 10 min, values close to 5.6 were measured (mild acidification) and at 15 min pH ranges were near or slightly up 5.9 (acidic environment). This trend indicates that acid washing process has succeeded to reduce the pH of fabric with the highest change happened between 5th minute and 10th minute. The mild acidic pH at 15 min might suggest that the acid wash was still in contact with the fabric damaging to fiber properties as also seen by changes in tear strength and color fastness.

3.6 GSM Measurement

Table 2: GSM observations of the samples

Samples	GSM (oz/yd ²)
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Before Wash	7.67
Wash for 5 min	8.49
Wash for 10 min	8.40
Wash for 15 min	8.43

The GSM (grams per square meter) of the acid-washed denim fabric shows a slight rise in weight after washing. Fabric gsm before wash is 7.67 oz/yd². 5 minutes of washing, the GSM rises to 8.49 oz/yd², revealing a partial swelling or intake of water during the washing. The GSM stabilizes at around 8.40 oz/yd² thereafter (after 10 minutes), but slightly further increases to 8.43 oz/yd² after 15 minutes of testing. It may be concluded that the fabric weight of KN acid washed cotton is slightly increased, probably attributed to the water retention or alterations in fibre morphology. The relation is only a modest increase, showing that the washing treatment does not lead to loss of mass fabric, however with possible minor modification in fabric density.

4. CONCLUSION

This work provides the insight about how acid wash duration affect both the performance and appearance of denim garments. From the observations, it was determined that washing time changes more than surface shade. 5 min wash provides a only mild fading and kept the mechanical properties less affected whereas 15 min washed samples faded more with noticeable reduce of tear strength and sharper drop in pH. The 10 min washed treatment offers more uniform fade without compromising excessive damage. This findings proves a practical guideline for denim manufacturers a moderate wash time, offers the best compromise between style and performance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our profound appreciation to Creative Wash Ltd - 04. in Bangladesh for kindly giving the lab space we needed to carry out our research.

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